
Generic Assessment and Evaluation Reference Model

GAERM

2026-03-31

Copyright © 2026 University of Essex. Created by UK Data Archive, UK Data Service.

Version 05.00

Table of Contents

Introduction	3
Overview	4
Entities, Attributes & Evidence	5
Governance: Bodies, Criteria, Processes	6
Governance Policy	6
Criteria	6
Assessment Process	7
Evaluation Method: Metrics & Tests	7
Outcome	8
Validity Terms	9
Status	9
Corrective Actions	9
Artefacts, Actors, Agents & Roles	10
Concluding Remarks	10
Version History and Acknowledgements	12
Authors	13

Introduction

As domains of practice evolve and mature, they tend to develop common practices. To support consistency and provide the foundation for further improvement these approaches may be collated into criteria against which entities are assessed. This paper¹ describes a generic model to support the development, implementation and comparison of assessments in terms of the necessary concepts, actors and processes.

Standards are the “specification of precise criteria to be used consistently and appropriately” (Ruusalepp et al²), that may be either *normative*—setting requirements for quality and actions, or *informative*—describing and guiding the use of methods. To be inclusive of more and less formally structured and managed approaches the broader term ‘criteria’ is used here.

Criteria may be applied to a wide variety of entities (any ‘thing’: object, person, process, organisation, software, etc.). Entities may be compared against criteria through assessment and evaluation by third parties, including peers, or through self-assessment.

Assessment processes range from a check that an XML file conforms to a declared schema, to full, formal ISO standard audits of organisational practice. Within an assessment process an ‘evaluation’ compares some defined attributes (skills, quality levels, capabilities etc) of an entity to the criteria. Evaluation methods may be entirely machine-actionable, mediated by human actors, or a mixture of the two.

The outcome of an evaluation confers a status on an entity after comparing evidence about the attributes of the entity against defined criteria.

Diagram A: Assessment Process: Entity, Attributes, Evidence, Criteria and Status

¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.19347369>

² Raivo Ruusalepp, Christopher A. Lee, Bram van der Werf and Matthew Woollard, ‘Standards Alignment’ in Nancy Y. McGovern, ed., *Aligning National Approaches to Digital Preservation* (Atlanta, GA: Educopia Institute, 2012), pp. 115-166.

The Generic Assessment & Evaluation Reference Model (GAERM) expands on these central concepts to describe the necessary actors and governance required. The model also defines the components of assessments and evaluation methods, including metrics, tests, outcomes and validity terms.

An applicant may take corrective action to improve, based on the outcome of an assessment process. An assessment process may also reveal issues with the criteria, metrics or tests that require corrective action by a governing body.

Overview

An **assessment process** compares **evidence** about the attributes of an **entity** to criteria. An **evaluation method** applies **metrics** and **tests** to reach an **outcome**. As a result, a **status** is conferred on the entity.

- ❑ A **governing body**³ manages:
 - ❑ **Itself**, according to a
 - ❑ **Governance Policy**
 - ❑ **Criteria** and an
 - ❑ **Assessment process**
- ❑ An **applicant**⁴ is a representative for the **entity** in the **assessment process**, with a defined relationship to the entity and the evidence
- ❑ seeking to procure a **status** for the **entity** as an **outcome** of the **evaluation method**
- ❑ An **assessor** (human actor and/or machine agent) undertakes the **assessment process**
- ❑ The **assessment process** compares **evidence** about the **attributes** of the **entity** to the criteria
- ❑ An **evaluation method** applies **metrics** and **tests** to reach an **outcome**
- ❑ The outcome has **validity terms**
- ❑ A **status** may be conferred on the **entity**

³ The criteria and the assessment may be managed by different bodies. More than one body may offer assessment against a set of criteria.

⁴ In some cases, an assessment process may be applied to an entity by a third party without an applicant being involved.

Diagram B: Generic Assessment & Evaluation Reference Model

Entities, Attributes & Evidence

An entity can be any “thing”⁵: object, person, process, organisation, software, etc.

- ❑ The entity must be clearly and unambiguously identified.
- ❑ The attributes of an entity that are relevant to the criteria must be defined.

Example types⁶ of attributes of entities:

- Research skills of a person
- Checksum of a digital object
- Completeness of a metadata record
- Long term preservation capability of a repository
- Information security level of a data environment
- Functionality of a piece of software
- Conformance of an XML file

⁵ In the broadest sense, not in a formal ontological sense, so not ‘owl:thing’.

⁶ In the general sense, not a formal typology.

- Quality of a product or service
- Trustworthiness of a Data Repository
- FAIRness of a Digital Object
- ❑ Evidence is provided about the attributes of the entity

Evidence could include:

- Structured metadata characteristics
 - PID of a digital object
 - Size in GB of a data collection
 - Level of curation and preservation from a controlled vocabulary
- Less structured information artefacts
 - Policies, procedures or other documentation
 - Information published to the internet
 - A written response to an examination paper
 - Content from an internal wiki

Evidence may be assessed entirely by the process or may partially depend on third parties, such as a validation authority e.g. validating claims of repository certification status with a certification body.

Governance: Bodies, Criteria, Processes

A governing body manages itself, criteria and an assessment process according to a governance policy.

Governance Policy

The governance policy:

- ❑ Defines the authority of the governing body
- ❑ Describes the management (including change management) of the:
 - ❑ governance policy
 - ❑ criteria
 - ❑ assessment process
 - ❑ status

Criteria

The criteria against which the attributes of the entity will be assessed based on evidence:

- ❑ The criteria can be any stable set of clear expectations capable of being assessed
- ❑ The criteria must clearly specify the entities they apply to

Examples of entities:

- Digital Objects

- People
- Organisations
- Processes
- Software

Examples of criteria.

- Technical specification
- Certification standard
- Rights statements
- Policies
- Legislation
- Guidance

Assessment Process

An assessment compares evidence about the attributes of the entity to criteria according to a process defined by a governing body. Assessment may be an ongoing, informative monitoring process as well as including one or more evaluation methods with a range of outcomes.

The assessment process must:

- Be a defined set of actions
- Define the evaluation method(s)
- Define all possible outcomes
- Define validity terms
- Define the status to be conferred on an entity

Evaluation Method: Metrics & Tests

An assessment process confers a status, based on outcomes, with validity terms, through an evaluation method. In the evaluation method, the criteria are associated with metrics and tests⁷. A metric can range from a defined objective measure to a subjective opinion, or any combination of approaches. One or more tests are used to assess evidence to see if each metric has been achieved. In an evaluation method:

- Each criterion is assigned one or more metrics
- Each metric is assigned one or more tests
- All possible results of individual metrics and tests are documented
- All combined results of metrics and tests are documented
- Any dependencies for test completion that are not directly related to metrics are documented⁸

⁷ Criteria may or may not already be granular and specific metrics with associated empirical tests.

⁸ E.g. If a test only understands information in RDF format and will not recognise XML.

In the evaluation process:

- One or more tests are used to validate whether a metric is achieved
- One or more metrics are used to validate whether a criterion has been achieved
- The individual and combined results of tests and metrics inform outcomes

If different tests and metric results interact, the interaction should be defined.

Examples:

- Each of the criteria is measured separately on a scale from 0-5, the final result is a cumulative score without weighting
- Public vote with final decision by the judges

Tests may cumulatively evaluate whether a metric has been achieved through multiple steps. Multiple different tests may be used to evaluate the same metric. Given the potential complexity of implementation, particularly for machine actionable evaluations, transparency is critical to maintaining confidence in the outcome of the assessment and to enable corrective action by the applicant (and the governing bodies).

Tests may:

- Fail to complete
- Accept evidence provided (e.g. checksum is available)
- Internally validate evidence provided (e.g. checksum matches digital object)
- Externally validate evidence provided (e.g. confirm claims of certification via a certification body)

The results of an evaluation method inform an **outcome** which has **validity terms**.

Outcome

Outcomes are separate from Evaluation Methods, e.g. a “PASS” outcome could be derived from a cumulative result of 60/100 or of 80/100.

- All of the possible outcomes must be defined

The successful completion of an evaluation method delivers an outcome that concludes whether an entity conforms to the criteria:

- Conforms
- Does not conform
- Partially conforms

However, there are an additional range of outcomes:

- Sufficient tests not completed to reach a conclusion
- Tests completed but evidence not sufficient to reach a conclusion
- Entity is out of scope for the criteria

- ❑ Each outcome must have associated validity terms.

Validity Terms

Validity terms are the set of rules related to an outcome.

- ❑ Validity terms for each possible outcome must be defined

For example:

- An outcome could be valid for a defined time period
 - The entity is certified for 5 years
- There may be a right to appeal
 - The applicant may request an alternate reviewer
- There may be terms associated with repeating the evaluation
 - The applicant cannot re-apply for 6 months
 - The entity may only be re-evaluated if the evidence is revised
- Further evaluations may be required to maintain the outcome
 - The applicant must undertake ongoing internal audits to maintain certification

Status

As a result of the outcome of the assessment process a status may be conferred on the entity.

For example:

- A file is unchanged (*has integrity*)
- An XML file is valid (*conforms to schema*)
- An object is *FAIR*
- A repository is *certified*
- A publication is *open access*

Corrective Actions

An applicant may take corrective action to improve based on the outcome of an assessment process. An assessment process may also reveal issues with the criteria, metrics or tests that require corrective action by a governing body.

Applicant/Entity Corrective Action:

- Add or change the evidence provided in response to changes in the Entity
- Expose evidence in a way that ensures a test will complete

Governing Body Corrective Action:

- Applicant appeals against an outcome. The assessment is repeated, and the outcome is changed

- Applicant proposes a change to process, criteria, metric or test
- Governing body identifies an issue and proposes a change

Artefacts, Actors, Agents & Roles

- ❑ Artefacts must be defined

The minimum artefacts to be defined in creating an assessment and evaluation framework are: governance policy, entity/attributes definitions, criteria, and an assessment process (including evaluation method, outcome and validity terms).

This generic model does not specify how these different artefacts should be grouped or presented.

- ❑ All roles must be defined

Governing body, applicant and assessor are the minimum roles to be defined.

- ❑ How roles interact with artefacts must be defined

The governance policy, criteria and assessment process must all be associated with a governing body.

- ❑ How roles interact with other roles must be defined

This reference model presents a single governing body for simplicity, but different artefacts may have different governing bodies. If there is more than one governing body, interactions between them must be defined

- ❑ Each role must be undertaken by a clearly identified actor/agent

When an assessment and evaluation framework is implemented all roles must be associated with clearly identified actors (people, groups or organisations) or agents (machines, software).

Concluding Remarks

The generic model seeks to define the minimum set of terms and concepts necessary to consistently describe an assessment and evaluation framework. The model supports the development, implementation and comparison of such frameworks⁹.

It is increasingly likely that entities will need to comply with more than one framework. Comparison of frameworks using the generic model helps us consider the impact on applicants, including resource implications. The model may also support applicants in

⁹ A number of proposals and projects around the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and FAIR data envision the development or expansion of entity assessment and evaluation. These are intended to demonstrate good practice and to support rules of engagement between the people, processes and technologies that comprise data infrastructures. Targets for assessment and evaluation include digital objects, data repositories, metadata registries, software and services.

developing business information management systems that can efficiently maintain evidence for multiple assessment and evaluation frameworks

There are a number of characteristics of assessment and evaluation that the authors consider important, but out of scope for the model. For example it is assumed that:

- beneficial outcomes (and hence conferred status) for the applicant, and confidence in the governing body are necessary conditions for a successful framework.
- confidence in a framework is increased by maximising the transparency of entity definitions, governance, standards and processes (including evaluation methods, outcomes and validity terms).

The next steps are to seek further feedback on the reference model and to develop examples based on evaluation frameworks that exist or are in development. Examples will be used to validate the model. Subsequent versions of this document will amend, clarify, correct, reduce or expand the model as necessary.

Version History and Acknowledgements

Version	Notes	Date
05.00	Updated to use the UK Data Service document template. Minor corrections to the text.	2026-03-31
04.00	This version retains references to 'standards' but broadens applicability to a range of 'criteria' that may be less formally defined or managed. It adds the concepts of metrics and tests and incorporates possible corrective actions (by applicants or governing bodies).	2024-07-30
03.00	In response to feedback from trainers and educators this version has been amended to use the 'assessment' and 'evaluation' in ways that more clearly align with the teaching and academic use of the terms. The title of the paper has been updated to reflect the co-dependence of these concepts.	2020-03-30
02.00	The authors would like to thank members of the CoreTrustSeal Board, the CESSDA Trust Working Group and the FAIRsFAIR project for their feedback on version 1. The diagrams and structure of the document have been refactored as a result to increase clarity and reduce repetition.	2019-10-01
01.00	The authors would like to thank Professor Matthew Woollard for his initial feedback on the model including elaboration on the interactions between entities, attributes and evidence.	2019-06-11

Authors

Name	Roles, Affiliations, Identifiers
Hervé L'Hours	Associate Director: Repository & Data Infrastructure Services Harmonisation. UK Data Service, UK Data Archive, University of Essex. https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5137-3032
Darren Bell	Associate Director: Technical Services. UK Data Service, UK Data Archive, University of Essex. https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4152-6549
Oliver Parkes	Repository Project & Standards Coordinator. UK Data Service, UK Data Archive, University of Essex. https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2142-6081

www.ukdataservice.ac.uk

help@ukdataservice.ac.uk

+44 (0) 1206 872143

We are supported by the Universities of Essex, Manchester, Edinburgh, University College London and Jisc. We are funded by UKRI through the Economic and Social Research Council.